

DEVELOPMENT OF A CREATIVE APPROACH WHEN TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE TO ART STUDENTS.

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Abstract: This article discusses the specific difficulties that art students encounter while studying English as a second language. It suggests a creative teaching method that utilizes their visual talents and artistic sensibilities. It examines the specific issues faced, analyzes the root causes, and suggests practical solutions to improve their language-learning journey.

Keywords: specific difficulties, vocabulary gap, utilize artwork, teaching method.

Introduction: The art world is by nature international, surpassing language barriers. For art students who are learning English as a second language, understanding the intricacies of the language in the art field can be difficult. While their artistic skills flourish, the root question in English may lag behind, hindering their ability to communicate their creative vision effectively. This article examines the distinctive challenges of teaching English to art students and suggests an innovative method that utilizes their artistic abilities to maximize their capabilities.

Problems: Vocabulary Gap: Art students frequently come across specialized terminology related to various art genres, techniques, and movements, making it challenging to understand and utilize. Lack of Contextual Understanding. The fear of mispronunciation or grammatical errors can lead to reluctance in verbalizing artistic ideas and engaging in discussions.

To address these problems, educators can employ an innovative method that integrates English learning with art education:

1. Visual Language Learning:
2. Art-Based Storytelling: Utilize artwork to inspire storytelling and creative writing activities, prompting students to delve into narratives, symbolism, and emotional expression through language.
3. Visual Dictionary Development: Develop interactive visual dictionaries that explain art terms using images, examples, and real-life contexts.
4. Art History through Language: Merge art history conversations into language classes, examining artistic movements, important figures, and relevant vocabulary.

These problems stem from the disconnect between the dominant visual mode of communication in art and the primarily verbal nature of language learning. This disconnect can result in Limited Communication. Art students may struggle to articulate their artistic intentions and engage meaningfully in art critiques and discussions.

Solution: To bridge this gap, educators can adopt a creative approach that weaves English learning into the very fabric of art education. Engaging with Art Discourse: Art Critiques and Discussions, Facilitate structured art critiques that focus on developing analytical and descriptive language skills.

Guest Artists and Experts: Invite professional artists and art critics to lead discussions, providing authentic exposure to the language of the art world.

Art Blog Writing: Encourage students to write blog posts or art reviews, developing their ability to articulate their thoughts and opinions in written English.

Conclusion: ironmen that integrates art and language, educators can empower art students to overcome linguistic barriers and unlock their full artistic potential. This approach not only enhances their English proficiency but also enriches their understanding of art and its cultural significance. By leveraging their visual strengths and nurturing their love for art, we can help art students express themselves powerfully and confidently in the language of the world..

References:

1. McMillan, B. A., & Rivers, D. J. (2011). The practice of policy: Teachers attitudes toward “English only”. System, (39), 251-263. Morahan, M. (2007).
2. L1 Use in EFL Classes with English-only Policy: Insights from Triangulated Data. CEPS Journal Vol.5 (2), 162- 175
3. Salah, N. M. H. & Farrah, M. A. H. (2012). Examining the Use of Arabic in English Classes at the Primary Stage in Hebron Government Schools, Palestine: Teachers’ Perspectives. Arab World English Journal 3(2): 400- 436.
4. Shabir, M. (2017). Student-teachers’ beliefs on the use of L1 in EFL classroom: A global perspective. English Language Teaching. Vol 10(4).45-52. Sharma, B. K. (2006).
5. Mother tongue use in English classroom. Journal of NELTA 11(1), 80-87. Schweers, W. (1999).
6. Creative in the E and D (Technical report N30) (1978).
7. Нафиева А.Г. Креативная компетентность педагога: теоретический аспект. [Электронный ресурс] //

8. Молодежь и наука: реальность и будущее: Материалы III Международной научнопрактической конференции. – Невинномысск: НИЭУП, 2010. Том I: Культурология. Педагогика. – С. 315.
9. Соловьева О.В., Халилова Л.А. Креативность в структуре педагогического мышления будущих преподавателей высшей школы. [Электронный ресурс]
10. Прикладная психология и психоанализ: электронный научный журнал. 2010. №2. URL: <http://ppip.idnk.ru>
11. Шумовская А.Г. Командная работа как условие формирования креативной компетентности будущего педагога. Magister Dixit: электронный научнопедагогический журнал Восточной Сибири. – 2011, №1. URL: <http://md.islu.ru/sites/md.islu.ru/files/rar/nafievaag.pdf>